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● Description of a new species of the genus *Agalope* Walker, 1854 from China and Myanmar (Lepidoptera: Zygaenidae: Chalcosiinae)

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Abstract: A new species of the genus *Agalope* Walker, 1854 is described from Southeast Xizang, Southwest China and Kachin State, North Myanmar, viz. *A. hei* sp. nov. The new species belongs to *A. geoffi* species-group. The adult habitus and male genitalia of the new species and related ones are illustrated and compared.

Keywords: Burnet moth, Himalaya, Indochina, Oriental Realm, taxonomy

● 中国及缅甸产绢斑蛾属一新种（鳞翅目，斑蛾科，锦斑蛾亚科）

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摘要：本文描述了一个产自中国西南部及缅甸北部的绢斑蛾属新种，即何氏绢斑蛾 *Agalope hei* sp. nov.。本新种属于杰夫绢斑蛾种组 *A. geoffi* species-group。本文图示并比较了本新种与其近似种的成虫及雄性生殖器。

关键词：斑蛾，喜马拉雅，中南半岛，东洋区，分类学

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Introduction

The genus *Agalope* Walker, 1854 (type species *A. basalis* Walker, 1854, now a junior synonym of *Chalcosia hyalina* Kollar, 1844) is characterized superficially by the presence of a large orange patch at forewing base, the stalked M₂ and M₃ veins and the presence of a single transverse band on forewing (Huang *et al.* 2023). In genitalia structures, the genus can be distinguished from its relatives by the following characters: 1) in male genitalia, the posterior tegumenal projection is rod-like and smooth on the surface, without process extending anteriorly; 2) the uncus is straight or gently curved distally downwards in lateral view and 3) in female genitalia the ostial plate/lamella postvaginalis is vestigial. The genus *Agalope* was reviewed by Huang *et al.* (2023) and four species-groups, viz. *A. hyalina* species-group, *A. eronioides* species-group, *A. livida* species-group and *A. geoffi* species-group were recognized. The *A. geoffi* species-group is currently known by two species, *A. geoffi* Huang & Horie, 2023 and *A. liuzihaoi* Huang & Horie, 2023, both only known from limited samples collected from Southeast Xizang. The species-group is mainly characterized by the unique juxta structure in male genitalia, viz. juxta lobe thick, expanding distally and is covered with numerous scale-like spinules of different sizes (Huang *et al.* 2023). During the study of Chalcosiinae from China and adjacent countries, two males belonging to a possible new taxon were discovered during the field work conducted in Motuo County, Southeast Xizang, China in 2017 and the collection of KMNH from North Myanmar. After examining the male genitalia, it turns out that the two specimens represent a hitherto unknown new species of *A. geoffi* species-group and is described herein.

Material and methods

Specimens examined are deposited in the following institutional collections: South China Agricultural University (SCAU), Guangzhou, P. R. China; the Kitakyushu Museum of Natural History and Human History (KMNH), Kitakyushu, Japan and the Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change, Museum Koenig (ZFMK, former Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig), Bonn, Germany. Photos of imagoes were taken by a Sony DSC-RX100 v1.00 camera. Abdomens were removed and macerated in hot 10% NaOH or KOH solution for examination of male genitalia. Photos of genitalia were taken under a Keyence VHX-5000 or a VHX-2000 digital microscope. Adult and genitalia photos were all processed by Adobe Photoshop CS5 ® software. Terminology of adult and genitalia morphology follows Yen *et al.* (2005) and Huang *et al.* (2023). Abbreviations used in the legends to the illustrations: HT = holotype, PT = paratype.

Taxonomy

Genus *Agalope* Walker, 1854 绢斑蛾属

Agalope hei sp. nov. 何氏绢斑蛾

<https://zoobank.org/E7FD4479-5582-458E-8223-567A98A00D7D>

Figs 1, 2, 5

Type material. **Holotype** (Figs 1, 5): male, 22.VII.2017, 62K, Motuo County, Xizang, P. R. China, leg. Si-Yao Huang, Shi-Fang Mo, Fu-Hong Wei & Shu-Qin Ji (SCAU). **Paratypes**: 1 male, 17.Sep.1996, Kachin, N. Myanmar, ex. coll. T. Endo (KMNH).

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to Mr. Mu-Yang He (Jiangxi, China) for his constant help during the study on Chalcosiinae of the first author.

Diagnosis. Externally, *Agalope hei* sp. nov. can be distinguished from the two congeners in the *A. geoffi* species-group by the combination of the following characters: 1) on hindwing, the tornus area is suffused with greyish scales, while in *A. geoffi* (Figs. 3, 6) and *A. liuzihaoi* (Figs. 4, 7) the tornus area is white; 2) on hindwing, the cilia are greyish from apex to tornus, while in *A. geoffi* the cilia are greyish from apex to cell Cu₂ and white from cell Cu₂ to the tornus, and in *A. liuzihaoi* the cilia are white from apex to tornus. In male genitalia, the new species

differs from both congeners in the trapezoid distal saccular process (triangular in *A. geoffi* and rectangular in *A. liuzihaoi* with denticles at the distal margin) and the narrower distal section of sacculus. The phallus of the new species is nearly equal in length with that of *A. liuzihaoi* but slightly longer than *A. geoffi*.

FIGURES 1–4. Males of *Agalope* spp. Depositories of the specimens: 1 in SCAU 2 in KMNH 3 & 4 in ZFMK.

Male. Forewing length 19–21 mm in males. Antennae bipectinate. Head, thorax and abdomen black, thinly scaled. Both wings thinly scaled and translucent. Forewing upperside ground color white, with base orange-marked and one indistinct transverse band in medial zone, nearly fused with the darkish patterns in discal cell and the postdiscal and marginal areas of the wing. Postdiscal and marginal areas grey. Veins darkened. Cilia grey. Hindwing upperside ground color white white. Veins darkened at the distal section. A diffused greyish patch presented in the tornus area. Cilia totally greyish.

Male genitalia. Uncus trapezoid ventrally, slightly broader at base and gradually narrowed towards tip, with distal end truncate. Tegumen with rounded margins. Posterior teguminal projection rod-like and thick, smooth on the surface. Vinculum slender. Saccus rounded and broad V-shaped. Juxta U-shaped, lobes long (ca. 1.5 × posterior teguminal projection length), gradually widening towards the distal end and spatulate, covered with numerous triangular piliform spinules of different sizes. Valva relatively broad (ca. 1.5 × uncus length) and long (ca. 4 × uncus length), dorsally membranous; sacculus gradually narrowed towards its tip and forming an upturned and trapezoid process distally. Phallus simple, bending downwards medially.

Female. Unknown.

Distribution. Currently known from Southeast Xizang, Southwest China and Kachin State, North Myanmar.

FIGURES 5–7. Male genitalia of *Agalope* spp. Depositories of the specimens: 5 in SCAU 6 & 7 in ZFMK.

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Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization: S-Y Huang & K Horie. Project administration: S-Y Huang. Resources: S-Y Huang. Supervision: S-Y Huang. Visualization: S-Y Huang. Writing–original draft: S-Y Huang. Writing–review and editing: S-Y Huang & K Horie.

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